

INTERACTION OF CHARCOAL WITH IODINE IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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The interaction of charcoal with iodine in aqueous solution under different conditions has been studied in some details. The amount of iodine removed from solution by charcoal under standard conditions is influenced considerably by the nature of the charcoal surface. Such determinations therefore cannot be used for measuring surface areas of charcoal. An appreciable fraction of the iodine removed from solution is, in fact, converted into hydriodic acid, the corresponding amount of oxygen being chemisorbed by the charcoal, giving rise to CO_2 -complex. While a small amount of iodine is adsorbed reversibly by all types of charcoals, another small amount is adsorbed irreversibly by degassed charcoals only.

It appears from the literature that the results obtained by several workers on the adsorption of iodine by charcoals and carbon blacks (Herz and Lorenz, *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 47, 331; Smith *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1941, 33, 1303; Watson and Parkins, *ibid.*, 1955, 47, 1053; King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1489; Linner and Willman, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 605; Razouk and Shimi, *A'in Shams. Sci. Bull.*, 1953, 2, 203) are often at variance with one another. Smith *et al.* as well as King, and Linner and Willman have attempted to correlate iodine adsorption with surface area of the adsorbent, but the work of Watson and Parkins as well as that of Razouk and Shimi does not appear to confirm this conclusion.

The importance of measuring iodine adsorption under fixed conditions, such as, pretreatment of the adsorbent, the amount of the adsorbent used, initial concentration and quantity of the iodine solution used, ratio of KI/I_2 in the solution, time of contact, etc. has been rightly emphasised by Koide *et al.* (*J. Soc. Rubber Ind., Japan*, 1950, 23, 111). It was thought of interest to study the adsorption of iodine from aqueous solution by different samples of charcoal under standardised conditions and to gain an insight into the mechanism involved about which very little appears to have been reported so far.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two samples of charcoal, prepared by the carbonisation of cane-sugar and coconut shells, as described earlier (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 181), were used before as well as after degassing at 750° and 1200° . The surface areas of these samples were calculated from their water isotherms (Puri *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 841) by using Harvey's calculations (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2343).

Iodine solutions of concentrations varying from 0.05 to 0.30*N* were prepared in potassium iodide solutions of different concentrations.

Procedure.—One g. portions of each charcoal were mixed with 100 c.c. of the various iodine solutions. The suspensions were shaken mechanically in half-pound bottles, wrapped in thick black papers, for different intervals of time after which an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was examined for unchanged iodine and hydriodic acid formed, if any, by the usual analytical methods. The results of blanks did not show any fall in the concentration of iodine solutions under similar conditions.

Two g. portions of the various samples of charcoal (oven-dried at 110°) before as well as after treatment with iodine solution under optimum conditions were subjected to evacuation at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace and the gases evolved were analysed in an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus, as described before (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1958).

The pH values of the charcoal suspensions (1:5) were determined by using a Cambridge glass electrode pH meter.

The base-adsorption capacity (b.a.c.) was determined by shaking 1 g. charcoal with 100 c.c. of 0.2 *N* barium hydroxide solution for 48 hours and titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution in the usual way.

TABLE I

Amounts of iodine adsorbed by original sugar charcoal after shaking for 24 hours.

KI/I ₂ ratio.	Amount adsorbed (m.e./g.) when the concentration of the solution is:					
	0.05 <i>N</i> .	0.10 <i>N</i> .	0.15 <i>N</i> .	0.20 <i>N</i> .	0.25 <i>N</i> .	0.30 <i>N</i> .
3 : 1	3.10	3.40	4.30	4.85	5.00	5.03
4 : 1	2.50	3.60	3.68	3.85	4.05	4.05
5 : 1	2.00	2.65	2.90	3.30	3.55	3.59
6 : 1	1.90	2.15	2.58	2.80	3.15	3.12

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the results recorded in Table I that, for a given KI/I₂ ratio, the magnitude of adsorption increases with increase in the concentration of the solution and that the value becomes almost constant when the concentration is 0.25 *N*. It is also evident that the intensity of adsorption is influenced considerably by the amount of potassium iodide in the solution, and that for a given concentration of iodine solution, it increases with decrease in the KI/I₂ ratio. It appears that for maximum adsorption this ratio should not exceed 3:1. It was not convenient to prepare iodine solution of moderate concentrations in which this ratio was less than 3.

TABLE II

*Effect of time of shaking on the adsorption of iodine by original sugar charcoal from a 0.25 *N* iodine soln. containing 3 moles of KI per mole of iodine.*

Shaking time (hrs.)	2	4	6	8	12	24	48	96
Iodine adsorbed (m.e./g.)	2.20	2.95	3.51	3.90	4.39	5.05	5.12	5.10

It is seen (Table II) that mechanical shaking for a minimum period of 24 hours is necessary for the attainment of equilibrium when maximum value is obtained.

In all subsequent experiments 1 g. charcoal was mixed with 100 c.c. of freshly prepared 0.25*N* iodine solution containing 3 moles of potassium iodide per mole of iodine, and the suspension was shaken mechanically for about 24 hours.

The amounts of iodine adsorbed by the various samples of charcoal under these conditions are recorded in Table III. The surface areas of the adsorbents are also included. It is seen that neither sugar charcoal nor coconut-shell charcoal undergoes any noticeable decrease in surface area on evacuation. This is consistent with the previous observation of some other workers as well (Emmett and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1492; McDermot and Arnell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 492). However, iodine adsorption by each charcoal undergoes a considerable decrease on evacuation. It appears therefore that iodine adsorption is considerably influenced by the nature of the charcoal surface.

TABLE III

Iodine adsorption, surface area and pH values of the various samples of charcoal.

Samples.	Iodine adsorbed (m.e./g.).	Surface area (m ² /g.).	pH value.
Sugar charcoal :			
Original	5.10	425	2.85
750°-evacuated	3.75	420	6.98
1200°-evacuated	2.60	423	8.80
Coconut-shell charcoal :			
Original	3.80	361	3.38
750°-evacuated	2.91	362	6.90
1200°-evacuated	2.12	359	8.37

The pH values of the water suspensions of the various samples of charcoal are also included in Table III. It is seen that the original samples have fairly low and the degassed samples have fairly high pH values. It appears therefore that a low pH favours and a high pH hinders the adsorption of iodine. Thus adsorption of iodine does not provide a suitable method for estimating surface areas of carbons as considered by some workers (*loc. cit.*).

Mechanism of Iodine Adsorption by Charcoal.—To ascertain the mechanism involved in the adsorption of iodine from aqueous solution by charcoal, the supernatant liquid, after shaking 1 g. portions of the various samples with 100 c.c. of 0.25 *N* iodine solution, was carefully analysed for iodine left unchanged and for hydriodic acid formed. The charcoal, after the treatment, was thoroughly washed, first with water and then with CCl₄ to remove the reversibly adsorbed iodine. It was then dried at 110° in an air-oven and subjected to evacuation at 1200° to find out the amount of oxygen chemisorbed, if any, during the process. The gaseous mixture above each reaction bottle was also analysed to see if any oxygen or oxides of carbon were formed during the process, but there were none.

TABLE IV

Account of iodine removed from solution after interaction with charcoal together with increase in oxygen content of the sample.

Samples.	Iodine added.	Iodine removed from soln.	HI formed.	Iodine recovered on washing (reversibly adsorbed).	Iodine adsorbed irreversibly (by diff.).	Iodine recovered on evacuation at 1200°.	Increase in O ₂ content evolved as CO ₂ .
(Results are expressed in m.e./g.)							
Sugar charcoal :							
Original	25.00	5.00	4.07	0.93	Nil	Nil	4.00
750°-evacuated	25.00	3.80	2.75	0.60	0.45	0.38	2.70
1200°-evacuated	25.00	2.71	1.80	0.56	0.35	0.36	1.78
Coconut-shell charcoal :							
Original	25.00	3.85	3.23	0.62	Nil	Nil	3.12
750°-evacuated	25.00	2.95	2.05	0.50	0.40	0.32	2.08
1200°-evacuated	25.00	2.20	1.48	0.35	0.37	0.35	1.50

The results of these experiments are recorded in Table IV. It is seen, in the first instance, that an appreciable proportion of the amount of iodine removed from solution (col. 3), which has been usually attributed to 'adsorption', actually represents the amount converted into hydriodic acid (col. 4), presumably by the hydrolysis of iodine brought about in the presence of charcoal. The amount of oxygen evolved in the reaction appears to be chemisorbed by the charcoal as there

is a considerable increase in the amount of CO_2 evolved on degassing each sample after the treatment (Table V). This increase, calculated as oxygen (col. 8, Table IV) is seen to be almost exactly equivalent to the amount of HI formed (col. 4).

It may be mentioned that there was no increase in the amount of CO_2 or H_2O evolved from any sample of charcoal after the treatment. This shows that the oxygen chemisorbed by the charcoal during the process gives rise to CO_2 -complex only.

TABLE V

B.a.c. of charcoal in relation to CO_2 evolved on evacuation at 1200° before and after treatment with iodine soln.

(Results are expressed in m.e./100g.)

Samples.	$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$	CO_2	$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$	CO_2
	neutralised.	evolved on evacuation.	neutralised.	evolved on evacuation.
	Before treatment.		After treatment.	
Sugar charcoal :				
Original	677.82 m.e./g.	686.40 m.e./g.	880.50 m.	886.40
750° -evacuated	Nil	Nil	59.88	135.05
1200° -evacuated	Nil	Nil	35.25	88.99
Coconut-shell charcoal :				
Original	312.45	317.00	466.95	472.05
750° -evacuated	Nil	Nil	49.46	104.10
1200° -evacuated	Nil	Nil	30.25	75.00

It is seen (Table IV) that while in case of the original samples, the entire amount of iodine removed from solution (col. 3) can be accounted for as hydriodic acid formed (col. 4) and iodine adsorbed physically or reversibly (col. 5) in case of the evacuated samples, a small amount of iodine remains unaccounted for. It appears therefore that unlike the original samples, the evacuated samples can fix a small amount of iodine irreversibly which probably becomes fixed at some unsaturated sites created by the elimination of the chemisorbed gases during the preliminary high temperature evacuation treatment. Small portions (about 1 g.) of these samples, after the treatment with iodine, were degassed at 1200° in a separate experiment to find out whether any of the 'fixed' iodine was eliminated at this temperature. The gases evolved were passed through a solution of potassium iodide which was titrated afterwards against a standard sodium thiosulphate solution in the usual way. The amount of iodine, thus recovered, is shown in column 7 and is seen to be fairly close to the amount which could not be accounted for (col. 6).

It is evident from the results recorded herein that not only the magnitude of the so-called 'adsorption' of iodine from aqueous solution by charcoal but even the course of the reactions involved are largely influenced by the *nature* of the charcoal surface.

The amounts of barium hydroxide neutralised and the amounts of CO_2 evolved on degassing at 1200° in case of the various samples of charcoal are recorded in Table V. It is seen that both the values increase as a result of the treatment with iodine solution. However, the two values are in close agreement only in case of the original samples. In the evacuated samples the amount of alkali neutralised is considerably less than the amount of CO_2 evolved. This shows that the CO_2 -complex formed on evacuated charcoal by iodine treatment differs from that formed in original charcoal in as much as it is not completely titratable against alkalis.